

INVESTIGATION, ANALYSIS AND FABRICATION OF HYBRID TOOL

Mr. R SURESH BABU, M. Tech, Assistant Professor

*Naresh Babu B, Srinath M, Vishal Ragavender V, Hariharan M G Department of Mechanical Engineering
Saranathan College of Engineering, Trichy, Tamilnadu, India-620012*

ABSTRACT: Most of the machine parts can be created by any one of the various manufacturing methods such as forging, machining, casting or welding methods. Choice of the manufacturing method depends on production costs of the alternatives for individual parts. Turning, grinding, lapping, etc. are the most common surface machining processes commonly employed in all manufacturing units to develop the components having high quality. The main aim of this project is to design and fabricate a suitable attachment for cylindrical grinding machine to turn cylindrical rods. It reduces the machining time to grinding cylindrical rods in cylindrical grinding machine to. This attachment is very economical when compared to all other attachments that are used to turn and grind at same place/simultaneously.

KEYWORDS: Tool attachment, Turning, Grinding.

I. INTRODUCTION

Machining plays vital role for developing the product to the customer needs. The choice of manufacturing methods like, machining, welding, casting, etc. are essential in the manufacturing environment out of which turning and grinding operations are the very important operations in the shop floor. For conducting these operations, we need Lathe and Cylindrical grinding machine. To make these processes easier we have attempted to develop the attachment for conducting the turning operations in cylindrical grinding machine to reduce the cost.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Marco Leonesio, Giacomo Bianchi, Jeremi Wójcicki [1] studied the present invention relates to a grinding machine comprising a first and a second grinding wheel separated by a gap and configured to contact a workpiece; a support blade positioned in the gap and having a contact surface having a work profile shaped to contact at one and only one point at a time the workpiece, and being further shaped to contact the workpiece with different working angles (γ), in different respective working steps.

Jörg Hartig, Benjamin Kirsch, Marco Zimmermann, Jan C. Aurich [2] experimented the cutting-edge preparation with elastic bonded super abrasive grinding wheels enables the accurate manufacture of customized cutting edges. This process necessitates highest accuracies of the machine and the kinematics. Up to now, no systematic investigations on the interaction of the metal working fluid and the grinding wheel were done; those could alter the properties of the grinding wheel, and as a consequence the result of cutting-edge preparation. The influence of this interaction on cutting edge preparation is investigated in this study using two different experimental setups. One setup where the grinding wheels interacted with the metalworking fluid in an aging chamber to speed up the aging process and one setup directly in a tool grinding machine, in which the grinding wheels were also applied for cutting edge preparation at different stages of aging.

Umesh Khandey [3] carried out experimentation on surface roughness of in case of single point cutting tool and from his experimentation he concludes that reduction in cutting tool flank wear also increases tool life. Multi-response optimization problem has been solved by searching an optimal parametric combination, capable of producing high surface quality turned product in a

relatively lesser time and at the same time ensuring reduced flank wear of the cutting tool.

Ranjeet Bagh, Purushottam Sahu [4] presented the mathematical modelling and parametric optimization on material removal rate, Machining Time, and surface roughness in turning operation of AA6063 steel with cemented inorganic compound coated atomic number 74 insert tool underneath different cutting parameters. The improvement of grey relational grade from initial parameter combination (a3–be–c3) to the optimal parameter combination (a1–b1–c1) is found to be 0.520 using grey relational analysis coupled with Taguchi method for simultaneous optimization of responses.

Mehdi Heidari, Javad Akbari, Jiwang [5] advised the effect of tool rack angle and nose radius on surface quality of ultra-precision demand formed porous silicon with FEM and Ultra Precision lathe technique Raman spectroscopy and stated that the decrease in rack angle influence the depth of high stress region.

S.A Afolalu [6] demonstrated the Impact of Heat Treatment on HSS Cutting Tool (ASTM A600) and Its Behavior during Machining of Mild Steel (ASTM A36) by employing the method of carburization of HSS and inferred that, increase in the feed rate and depth for length of cut of 50 mm significantly reduces the wear progression and thereby gave best machining time at maximum carburizing temperature and time (950oC / 120 minutes) when it was used to cut mild steel on the lathe machine.

A. Motallebia, A. Doniavi, Y. Sahebi [7] illustrated that Chatter is a self-excited vibration which depends on several parameters such as the dynamic characteristics of the machine tool structure, the material of the work piece, the material removal rate, and the geometry of tools. Chatter has an undesirable

effect on dimensional accuracy, smoothness of the work piece surface, and the lifetime of tools and the machine tool.

T.Nakagawa Suzuki [8] investigated the grinding center based on an NC turning center, has been developed for efficient external, internal or cam grinding of ceramic mechanical parts. The grinding center is provided with not only various grinding wheels, but also an ultrasonic grinding attachment for reducing grinding force during coring or expanding holes. The grinding center is also equipped with an on-machine wire electro-discharge trueing/dressing unit for metal bond diamond wheels. All the other revisions necessary for grinding ceramic materials have been made on the turning center.

Piyush Shah [9] worked on Explicit Dynamic Analysis of Single Point Cutting Tool using Different Tool Content for Variable Depth of Cut and also observed the stress and deformation patterns for both HSS and HCHC tool content an explicit dynamic analysis is carried out for the presented work to see the tool behavior at various points as the cutting proceeds.

Shuai Wang, Shu sen Zhao, Bin Li, Hua Bao and Zhan shu [10] studied the development of surface integrity theory, illustrates the important influence of surface integrity on the fatigue life of component, introduces the development and research status of grinding process, and states the theory and application of grinding process with superior surface integrity after the case hardening or surface modification of key component.

Barbacki kawalec [11] analyzed investigations concerning the surface layer alterations in hardened steels induced by turning with alumina and CBN edges and grinding with CBN grinders. The surface integrity parameters such as microstructure (investigated also with transmission electron microscopy (TEM) methods), microhardness, stress level and roughness were measured and

analyzed. Influence of turning and grinding parameters on the above characteristics have been considered.

Hemantkumar Junghare, Mayur Hamjade, C.K. Patil, S.B. Girase and Mandar M. Lele [12] aimed in improvisation of the grinding process for elastic materials like rubber, plastic, composites, metals, waxes etc. Nowadays, we find a lot of wastage of these materials. Some of them like plastic, artificial rubber composites are very much harmful for our environment. This research will basically help in cautious use of the above-mentioned pollutants. For example, Thermoplastics are difficult to grind small sized particle at ambient temperature because they are softening adhere in lumpy masses and clog screens.

Mahipal B. Padhiyar and Vidya Nair [13] addressed a Comparative Study and Optimization of Surface Roughness using Different Cutting Parameters in Turning with Taguchi's design of experiment and found that from the two tools lowest surface roughness is met in the TNMG tool 0.648 micron and the highest desirability is met in DNMG tool so, we get minimum surface roughness in TNMG tool 0.648, which is the minimum surface roughness all over the experiment.

Amber Batwa [14] illustrated a Study of Process Parameters on Machining Process Using Single Point Cutting Tool by the influence of cutting process parameters used in single point cutting tool-based machining operations and concluded that best parameter combination for FEM results is obtained in first case.

Deore Dhirajet [15] demonstrated the optimization and evaluation of cutting forces in turning operation of ENI 9 steel. In this optimization technique used is Taguchi method and analysis of variance is done to find which

parameters have significant effect. It is found out that feed is the most significant factor followed by speed which influences the feed force. For tangential force Depth of cut followed by feed is the significant factor.

III. PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

The most frequent problems during Grinding & Turning include;

- Depth of cut is limited
- High cutting forces are generated
- Grinding with the wrong process parameters.
- Grinding with wrong and/or wrongly aligned nozzles.
- Grinding wheel loading.
- Insufficient cooling during grinding

IV. OBJECTIVE

The main objective of this project is,

- To design and develop the attachment for conducting the turning operations in cylindrical grinding machine.
- To reduce the time spent to rework run-outs.
- To reduce the manufacturing cost and finishing time

V. METHODOLOGY

After completing the fabrication of the shield, the original shield of the cylindrical grinding machine is removed. The fabricated shield is attached to the machine using nuts and bolts firmly. The tool holder is placed on the shield so that the drilled holes coincide. Then it is attached to the shield using 4 bolt and nuts. The tool is placed in the groove in the tool holder and fixed in this position using bolts. The depth of cut necessary is given by adjusting the tool using the bolts in the top face of the tool holder. Thus, the attachment is ready to perform turning and grinding operation. The work piece is held between the chuck firmly using dog. The machine is switched on and the work piece rotates at 60 rpm. Now the table is moved gradually from one end to another end. Both the turning and grinding operation takes place simultaneously. The heat generated during cutting action is removed by circulating the coolant. After the operations are over, the machine is switched off. The depth of cut can be increased by adjusting the bolts at the top of the tool holder. The procedure is repeated again for machining further.

VI. RESULTS AND OBSERVATION

The simulation analysis has been executed for the single point cutting tool and the results have been obtained. The obtained results are useful for supporting the manual design calculations which is been discussed in Chapter 4. The results have been tabulated which contains the physical properties of the single point cutting tool and the max – min load withstanding limits when the feed is given to the tool during the operation of Turning process.

Figure 1 – Meshing of Single point cutting tool

Figure 2 - Simulation analysis of Single point cutting tool

The CAD simulation results and the investigation study results of the single point cutting tool are correlated with each other and have a deviation below 10% which is too small and can be neglected according to the norms of design and fabrication process. This tool attachment can withstand up to maximum of around 678.558N of force when the feed is given through the cylindrical grinding machine.

Table 1 – Correlation of Simulation and Analytical results

CAD SIMULATION RESULTS [SOLIDWORKS]	DESIGN CALCULATIONS [ANALYTICAL RESULTS]
RESULTANT FORCES	RESULTANT FORCES
F(X) = 678.558N F(Y) = -85.595N	F(H) = 778.558N F(Y) = -95.595N

Hence the results are being correlated which the Hybrid tool attachment is safe and secure for the multi-purpose operation like turning and grinding in one common machine.

VII. CONCLUSION

This attachment is an important mass production tool in home appliances, automobiles, electrical, chemicals, aircraft, dies and marine industries. The use of Concomitant Manufacturing Framework is used in mass production due to the advantages like efficient use of energy, high quality, low production time and low energy expenditure. The tool attachment is compact and user friendly in which it can be easily erected in the grinding machine. The analysis justifies that the tool attachment is more efficient and executes more accurate turning and grinding operations. The combination of two process can be executed simultaneously which in turn reduce the machining time, cost and increases the rate of profit. The tool attachment can be used in all range of industries since it is cost efficient. This tool attachment motivates to design and fabricate much more tool attachments for all the other different combinations of mechanical operations.

VIII. REFERENCE

1. Marco Leonesio, Giacomo Bianchi, Jeremi Wójcicki (2022), “Grinding machine and method of operating such grinding machine”, Volume: 01, Page: 10.
2. Jörg Hartig, Benjamin Kirsch, Marco Zimmermann, Jan C. Aurich (2022), “Cutting edge preparation with elastic bonded diamond grinding wheels”, Volume: 38, Page: 350–371.

3. Umesh Khandey (2021), “Optimization of Surface Roughness, Material Removal Rate & Cutting Tool Flank Wear in Turning using Taguchi Approach”, Volume 1, Page: 10.
4. Ranjeet Bagh, Purushottam Sahu Review (2020), “On Optimization of Cutting Tool and Cutting Parameters in CNC Turning of Aluminum Alloy 6063 through using the Taguchi method”, Volume: 07 Issue: 12.
5. Mehdi Heidari, Javad Akbari, Jiwang Yan, (2019) “Effect of tool rack angle and tool nose radius on surface quality of ultra-precision diamond formed porous silicon”, Elsevier, Journal of Manufacturing Process, Volume: 37, Pg: 321-331.
6. S.A Afolaluet (2018), “Impact of Heat Treatment on HSS Cutting Tool (ASTM A600) and Its behavior during Machining of Mild Steel (ASTM A36)”, Volume: 02, Page: 10.
7. Motallebia, A. Doniavi, Y. Sahebi (2018), “An Analysis and Modeling of the Dynamic Stability of the Cutting”, Vol. 22, No. 41287–1299.
8. T.Nakagawa Suzuki (2018), “The grinding center based on an NC turning center has been developed for efficient external, internal or cam grinding”, Volume 27, Page: 352.
9. Piyush Shah (2018), “Explicit Dynamic Analysis of Single Point Cutting Tool using Different Tool Content for Variable Depth of Cut”, International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews, Volume 5, Issue.
10. Shuai Wang, Shu sen Zhao, Bin Li, Hua Bao and Zhan shu (2018), “Development and Application of Grinding process”, Volume: 1, Page: 10.

- 11.Barbacki kawalec A (2017), “Turning and grinding as a source of microstructural changes in the surface layer of hardened steel”, Volume: 18, Page: 376.
- 12.Hemantkumar Junghare, Mayur Hamjade, C.K. Patil, S.B. Girase and Mandar M. Lele (2017), “A Review on Cryogenic Grinding”, Special Issue- Page: 421.
- 13.Mahipal B. Padhiyar and Vidya Nair (2017), “Comparative Study and Optimization of Surface Roughness using Different Cutting Parameters in Turning” International Journal of Engineering Science and Computing, Volume 3, Issue 3, PP 5906-5911.-58 7 Issue No.3.
- 14.Amber Batwa (2016), “Study of Process Parameters on Machining Process Using Single Point Cutting Tool”, Journal of Communications Technology, Electronics and Computer Science, Issue 5.
- 15.Deore Dhirajet, (2016) “The optimization and evaluation of cutting forces in turning operation of ENI 9 steel”, International Journal of Engineering Technology, Management and Applied science, Volume 4, Issue: 4, Page: 107.